

Paper 1**INFORMATION ASSURANCE? *FROM MEANING TO FOUNDATION*****P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²**¹Executive Director, MCIS, Department of CIS, Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**Corresponding Author:** pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com**Abstract**

Information Assurance is one of the important area of Information Science and Technology in recent past. This is the advanced area of Information Security as well. Security is the prime focus for most of us today. The organizations and Institutions to Individuals everyone are interested and concern about this security and privacy related affairs. Information Assurance is the broader version of Security related affairs. It is mainly deals with assurance related to technological products and manual systems related to information and content. Initially within the security spectrum Cryptography treated as most valuable and important but gradually other areas have been developed viz. Computer Security, then Network Security, Web Security, Database Security etc. Gradually as a whole, these are treated as Information Technology Security; it is also important to note that many universities and researchers worked and thoughts about manual content's security related affairs and a new concept has been developed called Information Security. The field and nomenclature, IA i.e. Information Assurance is the latest of this security edition and this is talks about the manual and technological information security related affairs leading to design, development and formulation, framework of security related affairs for the organizations, institutions and individuals. This paper described the basics of Information Assurance with reference to its root and historical foundations, basics meaning and features. Paper also talks about the function of Information Assurance as a brief with special reference to the process of Information Assurance.

Keywords

Information Assurance, IT Security, Web Security, Network Security, Information Privacy, Information Security, Information Science, IT

1. Introduction

Information Assurance is about the application and integration of IT and Computing in the Security and Privacy domain. Importantly, Information Assurance professionals do both the technological part and affairs as well as manual information security and privacy related affairs leading to designing, development of planning and policies on different aspects viz.—

- Planning, designing, development of Information Management principles of the organizations, institutions and individuals [1].

- Designing, development and framing of Information Privacy and Security by manual tools and framework for the same.
- Policy formulation related to the Information and IT Security including Software Security, Database Security, Network Security, Web Security etc.

Information Assurance is thus as a whole responsible for the availability, integrity, authentication as well as confidentiality of the information systems. The Information Assurance is about tools, techniques, technologies, rules, policies, methods etc in respect of security, privacy etc [2], [5].

2. Objective and Agenda

The present work is a conceptual and theoretical work and thus it deals with following objectives and agenda, in brief—

- To know about the basics of Information Assurance with its basic components.
- To learn about the basic of Information Security and Assurance with special reference to the boarder and smaller areas.
- To learn about the features and function of Information Assurance in brief but in simple manner.
- To know about the advanced areas of Information Assurance with reference to the nature, characteristics of this field.
- To dig out the Information Protection Policy in brief and its requirement in Information Privacy, Security and complete Assurance.
- To learn about the Process of the Information Assurance in brief with special reference to the future potentials.

3. Information Assurance: *From the Root to Features*

As we know information assurance is a process of information privacy and security management with the help of manual and computation technology so it has different kind of process. The core of Information Assurance is supported by different kind of processes as Information Assurance deals with right information to the right people at right time so Information Assurance has the process of information risk management, trust management, appropriate architecture and so one [3], [4], [6]. Using this policy and process the information may be authentic. As information assurance is related with information security, so technological process also need to maintain for better result. Information Assurance is also associated with management principle so such management principle needs to follow up for better results. Information Assurance is talks about defending malicious hackers so practitioners in this fields is talks about and deals with following-

- Corporate Governance
- Issus related to regulation and standard of Information Assurance
- Auditing of Information Security
- Disaster recovery related to information system

4. Information Assurance: Smaller and Broader Zone

In respect of IT and Computing, the area and concept Information Assurance is a valuable name. Various kind of security related affairs viz. Information security, IT security, Network security, Database Security, Web Security etc are basically fall under the Information Assurance. Practically, Information Assurance is responsible for the managing as well as assuring of various kind of contents viz. information, data, and knowledge etc in different form. The Information Assurance is deals both the technological and policy solution to information and similar contents. The areas such as information privacy and security are an important area of IA [7], [9]. Information security is the smaller area of Information Assurance and various affairs leading to data and information uses, processing, storage, and transformation etc also fall under the IA. Most of the western countries use the term Information Assurance as an alternative of IT Security and Cyber Security also. There are two methods of Assurance of the Information viz.–

- **Computational Systems/ Technological systems.**
- **Traditional Systems/ Manual Systems.**

As far as technological systems following areas (i.e. all the areas of IT Security or Cyber Security) are fall under this—

- Database Security
- Network Security
- Web Security [8], [11].

We know that Information Assurance is broader field than IT security and Information security. And Information Security and Assurance professionals normally have the knowledge of following—

- Business and accounting
- User study and experience
- Fraud management
- Forensic science
- Management science
- System and security engineering etc.

Hence Information Assurance is a broader, interdisciplinary, and multi skill requirement based subject (Refer Fig: 1). Many government organizations, bodies and even govt. use the term Information Assurance for example govt. of United Kingdom, United States etc. The body and agency which are associated with Information assurance normally deals with affairs of system engineering, forensic investigation thread analysis, accounting and criminology.

Fig: 1-From smaller to broader areas of Security related affairs related to Information and Contents

In UK HMG Information Assurance standard 1 and 2 has been changed over HMG Information Security standard 2. This standard has been discussed about the principle and requirement of Information Assurance, Risk Management etc. Hence Information Assurance is about physical, technical and administrative control. Here data can be protected in different format (both in physical and electronic).

5. Function of Information Assurance

The area Information Assurance is deals with different purposes but among these few important are include (but not limited to)—

- With the help of Information assurance it is easily possible to make available information to all and right time.
- Information Assurance basically helps in Data and Information Privacy as well as protection from unauthorized means also illegal access.
- It is a fact that technological security lies on information, thus both information security and IT security can depend on Information Assurance.
- The virtue of homeland security such as terrorism, cyber terrorism, cyber war etc can be done scientifically with the help of Information Assurance.
- Information Assurance helps in mobile security and related means with technological and manual way.
- Different kind of security viz. network's privacy, security, database and its security, Network and its security may get wider success with Information Assurance[06], [10], [11].
- Design, implementation, development, modernization of secure database and information management system become possible with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.

- Cloud security, infrastructure management, and trust management of different components of IT may get the benefits of Information Assurance practice; both technically and manually.
- Various kind of strategies related to the risk management of information and technologies become possible with Information Assurance.
- Malicious attack prevention and hacking related affairs become easily managed with the help of Information Assurance practice.
- Fraud management systems it depends on IT Security and more dependable system creation, and here Information Assurance play a lead role.
- Information transparency, Governance of the contents and public right on information and IT become possible with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.
- Holistic development of manual and computational information system regarding security and privacy the core jurisdiction of Information Assurance, in different context.
- Designing, Developing and implementing Information (general and technological), Cyber and IT related policy and its framework are the basic component of Information Assurance practice.

6. Process Vs. Information Assurance

Information Assurance and Security requires various steps and process and among these few important are include—

- Information Assurance typically deals with few process normally they are treated as enumeration and classification of information assets to be protected.
- Information Assurance expert deals with the risk assessment and vulnerabilities of information dealing product.
- Information Assurance is also talks about threat management and here assessment is very important. Here assessment considers both probability and threat of avoiding vulnerabilities.
- Cost benefits analysis is also impotent point to be noted. The Information Assurance practitioner normally design and develop risk management.
- As per as risk management plan is concern it has different steps and point to be noted. Mainly; mitigating, eliminating, accepting, transferring, preventing, detecting, responding threats. For this different standard and guidelines may be follow up Information Assurance practitioners.
- Counter measurement is also important in Information Assurance process that includes policy and procedures related to firewall management, antivirus management, regular backup, configuration management etc.
- In Information Assurance process training and development is also a important name and here security related awareness program, training program on emerging technology should be initiated.
- In context of Human Resource Management a dedicated computer emergency response team to be established.

- Testing and evaluation of security is also very important and here proper steps should be initiated.

Hence Information Assurance is an iterative process and here risk assessment plan are very important. So, proper and routine basis evaluation and revision should be undertaken.

7. Information Protection Policy

Information protection policy is a kind of guidelines responsible for the processing, storage as well as transmission of sensitive information in different means. Information Protection Policy is an important component of Information Protection Policy which is responsible for ensuring as well as protection from different modification as well as disclosure. As far as Information Protection Policy is concerned following are important to noted—

- Should define who can have access to sensitive information.
- Should define how sensitive information is to be stored and transmitted (encrypted, archive files, unencoded, etc.).
- Should define on which systems sensitive information can be stored.
- Should discuss what levels of sensitive information can be printed on physically insecure printers.
- Should define how sensitive information is removed from systems and storage devices.
- Should discuss any default file and directory permissions defined in system-wide configuration files [6], [11].

Information Protection Policy is a broad area and thus following things are covered under this field and expert should follow these (viz.)—

- Network security and including Network security policy
- Computer security and including Computer security policy
- Information security and including Information security policies
- User account policy in different means
- Remote access policy for the information
- Internet and intranet security
- Industrial espionage
- Fair Information Practices and principles etc.

8. Conclusion

Cyber Security is a valuable concern these days for managing information and also risk management. Organizations and institutes of different kind are facing challenges on security as a result adequate and qualified man power required in this field of cyber and information security. Various aspects viz. Cloud Computing Security, Mobile Security, Risk Management etc are the major concern of current age. In today's Digital Age security is not only an issue but also a challenge. Various other organizations viz. Government body and Ministries, organizations, and individuals getting knowledge from the cyber world and as a result every organizations are

moving towards not only computational security related management but also manual information security and privacy. Hence Information Assurance concept is increasing rapidly. Apart from emerging computational security concerns viz. Data Security, Web Security etc for different alternative solutions.

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